

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

THE COMPOSITION OF TECHNOLOGICAL MODULES FOR ORIENTING OF BUILDING STRUCTURES DURING THE PROCESS OF THEIR INSTALLATION IN THE DESIGN POSITION

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Abstract

The article discusses approaches to the layout of technological modules for orienting building structures during their installation. The principles of structural and technological solution of construction with use of arranging technological modules according to functional characteristics are given. The expediency of arranging them by groups was noted. An innovative method of orientation using the physical phenomena of magnetism is presented. The method of determining the parameters of magnets for lifting building structures with using of universal lifting modules is given. The layout of technological modules for orientation of vertical and horizontal building structures is proposed. Based on the synthesis of gravitational, mechanical, magnetic principles, technological modules are formed. All this together makes it possible to expect an improvement in the technological indicators of the processes of erecting building structures when implementing the proposed solutions. on the basis of the expansion of the functional capabilities of the technological equipment, one can expect an improvement in the technological indicators of the installation, such as the accuracy of the installation, safety, and the shortening of the work execution time. schemes of work organizations and programming of executive movements of technological modules with their involvement in the system of construction works.

Keywords: construction orientation methods, structural and technological solution for construction, universal lifting modules, installation methods, mechanized construction equipment.

Introduction. The principles of layout of technological modules for the orientation of building structures are oriented to modern requirements for engineering, constructive and organizational approaches, which are aimed at ensuring the efficiency, accuracy and reliability of installation or orientation of structures. The main principles include the following:

1. Modularity and unification: development of standard technological modules that can be easily integrated among themselves; unification of connecting elements for quick installation.
2. Flexibility and adaptability: the ability of modules to adapt to different conditions of the construction site, types of structures and weather conditions; using adjustable mechanisms to adjust the orientation of the structure.
3. Accuracy: implementation of high-precision tools for positioning structures, such as laser levels, GPS systems or electronic theodolites; using sensors to control the orientation and position of the structure.
4. Strength and reliability: ensuring the strength of the modules to withstand significant loads during the

orientation of structures; use of materials resistant to mechanical, climatic and corrosion effects.

5. Energy efficiency: use of energy-efficient equipment to reduce installation and orientation costs; use of mechanisms with minimal energy consumption.

6. Safety: provision of means of protection against overload, accidents and malfunctions; ensuring ergonomics to minimize risks for workers.

7. Automation and digitalization: application of software for modeling orientation and assembly processes; using robotic modules that can perform operations automatically.

8. Logistic convenience: the possibility of easy transportation of modules to the construction site; compactness and convenience of storing modules in the assembled state.

9. Environmental friendliness: use of materials and technologies that minimize the impact on the environment; enabling reuse of modules for different projects.

10. Economic efficiency: optimization of the cost of production and use of modules; minimization of operating costs.

These principles form the basis for the development of effective solutions that contribute to the improvement of the manufacturability and accuracy of the installation of building structures [1]. It is necessary to ensure the possibility of forced orientation of building structures both for prefabricated construction and for monolithic structures. In the first case, orientation takes place at the initial stage when building structures are submitted to the installation area, followed by their alignment. Also, in fact, during the orientation of prefabricated structures, the structures themselves are freely moved and pulled to the design position, in some cases due to the use of certain mechanisms and equipment. For monolithic structures, orientation processes are mostly used for formwork contours or sliding formwork movement guides [2], [3]. In work [4] directions of functional layout of universal lifting technological modules are considered. The "orientation", "fixation", "retention" and other modules are considered here. For the most part, the considered modules are either stationary or have manual control. Today's trends in the development of construction sites show that the presence of power drives as part of technological modules significantly improves the quality indicators of technological processes, in most cases they are basically necessary, and the site is designed with the mandatory condition of ensuring the power supply of executive mechanisms [5].

Orientation modules are closely related to fixation and retention modules [6 - 11]. They are key elements in the technological process of installation and ensuring the stability of structures. Each of the modules performs specific functions that are aimed at ensuring accuracy, safety and efficiency of installation. Let's consider the main characteristics and purpose of each module:

"Orientation" module

Functions. Ensuring the exact location of the structure in accordance with the design axes and height marks, correcting the position of the structure during installation. **Components.** This includes geodetic equipment (tachometers, laser levels, GPS navigators for determining the exact location), mechanized equipment (jacks, screw lifts or systems for changing the position of the structure), basic markers (geodesic benchmarks for the orientation of the structure).

Features. Provides minimal deviations, is used for mounting columns, supports, frames and other building structural elements.

"Fixations" module

Functions. Temporary or permanent stabilization of the structure after its orientation, keeping the structure in the design position until the installation is completed or fixed with the main elements.

Components. This includes fasteners, fasteners, temporary supports.

Features. The use of quick-release elements to facilitate dismantling after completion of work, taking into account the occurrence of static and dynamic loads.

"Maintenance module"

Functions. Constant maintenance of the stability of the structure during operation, protection of the struc-

ture from external influences. **Components.** This includes permanent fasteners, reinforcing elements, shock absorption systems.

Features. It is calculated in accordance with the normative loads, integrated with the main load-bearing elements of the building.

Orientation modules are used at the first stage of installation, when aligning the structure in space. Fixation modules temporarily fix the structure after its alignment. Retention modules perform permanent fastening of the structure to ensure its stability during operation.

The purpose of the work. The technological requirements for the orientation of building structures include the following.

- **Orientation accuracy.** This is ensuring the compliance of the location of the structures with the project documentation, namely the compliance of positioning coordinates, angles of inclination, elevation marks with the design data. For this purpose, instruments for measurement and control (laser levels, total stations, GPS devices) are used in order to minimize tolerances in deviations.

- **Durability and stability.** This is the use of temporary supports or fasteners to ensure the stability of the structure during installation, with the mandatory condition of withstanding installation and external loads during the work.

- **Installation safety.** This is compliance with safety regulations due to ensuring the stability of structures at all stages of installation.

- **Orientation by axes.** This is an accurate verification of the position of the structures relative to the control axes and reference points established during the geodetic marking of the territory.

- **Fixation of structures.** This is the use of special quick-install fasteners (anchors, ties, bolted connections) that ensure reliable fixation and their control.

- **Consideration of external factors.** This is an assessment of external force and temperature influences that can affect the orientation process.

- **Organization of the process.** This is the development of technological maps or work performance schemes, their control, which takes into account all stages of orientation and fixation, training and testing of personnel knowledge.

- **Use of auxiliary equipment.** This is the development of measures for the mechanization of production processes, the use of mechanized equipment that facilitates manual work, partially or completely replaces it is envisaged.

- **Quality control.** This is the implementation of geodetic monitoring with a comparison of the results with the project results. In the case of BIM implementation, data exchange is carried out to avoid inconsistencies or interim reporting is formed.

- **Compliance with regulations.** This is compliance with state and building regulations in the field of installation of structures.

In our opinion, special attention should be paid to the use of auxiliary means when considering the methods and methods of orienting building structures, among which mechanized technological modules play an important role [12].

Gravitational orientation of building structures is a method in which structures or their elements are located and fixed in place mainly due to their own weight. This approach is used to ensure the stability and balance of structures without the need for additional fasteners or fixing elements, although in some cases additional methods may be used to increase safety [5].

In fig. 1 shows the scheme of gravity orientation of a vertical building structure using the example of a reinforced concrete column and an artificial load [3]. The

main problem of accurate positioning of such columns is the presence of an oscillating effect from the hook suspension of the cargo crane due to the flexible rope connection [13-15]. The same effect is accompanied by the installation processes of horizontal structures. Innovative is magnetic positioning of building structures, a technology that uses magnetic forces to precisely position, fix or manipulate building elements [4], [5].

Figure 1. Scheme of gravitational orientation of a vertical building structure: *a* – vertical orientation; *b* – horizontal orientation; 1 – mounted structure; 2 – connecting element; 3 – suspension; 4 – bypass block

It is proposed to use magnetic components in orientation modules for the installation of vertical and horizontal building structures. The main principles of magnetic positioning are the use of magnets (permanent or electric), the use of magnetic materials in structures, ensuring regulation and control of the generated magnetic field. In this case, the lifting force of magnets is decisive. For permanent magnets, the algorithm for determining the lifting force is as follows. Magnet characteristics are determined [9], [10]

- **Magnetic induction (B), T.**
- **Magnet contact area (A), m².**

Magnetic permeability of air (μ_0),
 $\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \text{ N/A}^2$

The properties of the cargo material are taken into account

- **Magnetic permeability of the material. For steel or iron, it can vary from 100 to 5000.**
- **Material saturation:** Considered if the magnetic induction exceeds the level at which the material saturates.

Calculated magnetic force (F)
 $F = B^2 \cdot A / 2 \cdot \mu_0$,

where:

- *F* — magnetic lift force (N),
- *B* — magnetic induction (T),
- *A* — magnet contact area (m²),
- μ_0 — magnetic permeability of vacuum ($4\pi \times 10^{-7} \text{ Gn/A}^2$).

Consideration of safety factors. In practice, the force may decrease due to: unevenness of the load's contact surface, the presence of an air layer between the magnet and the load; wear or corrosion of surfaces. To compensate for these factors, a safety factor (*k*) is introduced, which is usually equal to 1.5–3. Then the lifting force is defined as:

$$F_f = F/k.$$

The lifting force is calculated depending on the system configuration. If the magnetic system consists of several magnets, the total force is defined as the sum of the forces of individual magnets:

$$F_{\Sigma} = \sum nF_i.$$

Work conditions will be checked. Ambient temperature and additional forces that may act on the building structure are taken into account. The features of the electric drive system are defined for an electric magnet [11], [15]. Calculation of the power of the electromagnet depends on its design, characteristics of the winding, the current and voltage supplied. An electromagnet converts electrical energy into a magnetic field, which creates a lifting force. The algorithm for calculating the power of an electromagnet [9], [10]. The power of the electromagnet is determined by the formula:

$$P = I \cdot V$$

where:

- *P* — electrical power (Watt),
- *I* — current in the circuit (A),
- *V* — winding voltage (V).

The resistance of the winding is determined by Ohm's law:

$$R = \rho l / A,$$

where:

- R – winding resistance (Ohm),
- ρ – resistivity of the conductor material (Ohm·m),
- l – conductor length (m),
- A – conductor cross-sectional area (m²).

Taking into account the resistance, the power of the magnet can also be calculated as:

$$P = V^2 / R.$$

Magnetic inductance affects the creation of a magnetic field. It is determined by the formula:

$$L = \frac{\mu N^2 A}{l_m},$$

where:

- L – inductance (Gn),
- μ – magnetic permeability of the core material,

- N – the number of windings turns,
- A – cross-sectional area of the core (m²),
- l_m – magnetic path length (m).

Magnetic energy, which is stored in the magnetic field:

$$W = 0,5L \cdot I^2$$

where:

- W – energy (J),
- L – inductance (Gn),
- I – current (A).

Power losses in the electromagnet occur due to:

- **Joule heat: Heat losses of the winding conductor:**
 $P_t = I^2 R.$
- **Core losses: Hysteresis and eddy currents in the magnetic core.**

Total power including losses:

$$P_{\Sigma} = P + P_t$$

The scheme of operation of the orientation module using magnetic components is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the interaction of the induction device with the magnet:
 1- inductor; 2 – magnet; 3 – ferromagnet

In principle, the process of orientation of a building structure consists of three stages: capture, direction, landing (docking). It should be noted that from the point of view of orientation, it is advisable to reproduce the magnetic lifting force in the direction opposite to the direction of the gravitational forces. Most likely, justified from the point of view of saving energy resources is the partial compensation of the forces of gravity by the magnetic lifting force, and the main role will be performed by mechanical lifting equipment.

In the case of forced orientation of vertical structures, orientation modules are temporarily fixed on

mounted structures or on temporary holding frames. The shape of the active magnet should be toroidal, and ferromagnetic rods are installed on the mounted structures. This ensures the capture of the mounted structure. To direct the structure, it is advisable to use bipolar magnets that create a repulsive effect on ferromagnets. The magnets themselves are installed with the possibility of vertical forced movement. Thus, the landing of the structure occurs when the magnets are lowered relative to the body and the structure itself is lowered by the loading device (Fig. 3, a).

Figure 3. Scheme of the formation of the system of interceptor modules: *a* – orientation of vertical structures; *b* – orientation of horizontal structures: 1 – mounted structure, 2 – connecting element, 3 – suspension; 4 – diameter magnet; 5 – basic structure; 6 – magnet body; 7 – moving magnet

It is also advisable to use movable technological formwork modules [3] for orientation of vertical structures. This application is justified by the fact that when connecting the columns, it is necessary to perform monolithic concreting of their abutment zones. Then the technological module in the form of a vertical movable formwork, with the main functional purpose - "structural limitation" acquires the functions of "catching", "orienting", "landing". To orient the horizontal structures with using powerlifting modules [17], [18] it is necessary to form a system of magnets on the support structures and a corresponding system of bipolar magnets on the horizontal structure. At the same time, a slight levitation effect of the structure is artificially created within the influence of magnetic fields, which allows you to perform the orientation of a heavy building structure with significantly less effort. This potentially allows obtaining more accurate positioning of structures

on the site, and reducing the share of human labor during the installation of structures. The scheme of formation of the system of interceptor modules of horizontal structures is shown in Fig. 3, b. For horizontal structures, it is often necessary to ensure the possibility of pushing them to the design position. At the same time, bipolar toroidal magnets are placed on the horizontal structure, and toroidal magnets with extendable ferromagnetic rods are placed on the support structures.

For horizontal structures, it is also possible to exclude the use of crane equipment in the case of raising the supporting structures and lifting the horizontal building structure at the expense of lifting modules [4],[17]. In this case, the application of magnetic orientation is performed in the case of adjusting the position of the structure during lifting. Layout of technological orientation of universal lifting modules is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Layout of technological orientation modules: I – fixation module; II – capture module; III – orientation module; IV – supply module; V – module of magnetic orientation; a – layout of the technological module for vertical structures: 1 – mounted structure, 2 – supporting structure, 3 – the first block of the module; 4 – the second block of the module; 5 – moving belt b – layout of the load-lifting module for horizontal structures: 1 – support platform; 2 – moving platform in the vertical direction; 3 – supporting platform; 4 movable plate in the horizontal direction.

Such a principal scheme allows to significantly improve the technological indicators of the orientation of building structures due to the reduction of oscillating actions from the flexible connection of crane equipment and mounted cargo. Further development allows us to expect the introduction of remote-control systems, automation and robotization of processes.

Conclusions

- composition of technological methods according to functional purpose is the necessary actions aimed at identifying optimal technological sets for supporting construction processes;

- the development of the field of magnetism makes it possible to develop schemes for the application of positive phenomena of magnetism and diamagnetism to obtain in practice phenomena that reduce the dynamics of movements of mounted building structures when using crane equipment;

- the combination of gravitation, mechanical, and magnetic phenomena during the composition of technological modules allows synthesizing mechanized technological equipment in accordance with the installation tasks;

- on the basis of the expansion of the functional capabilities of the technological equipment, it is possible to expect an improvement in the technological indicators of the installation, such as the accuracy of the installation, safety, and the reduction of the terms of execution of works;

- the further development of technological module layout systems and, accordingly, the mechanized equipment of technological processes is predicted in the direction of analysis of the kinematics of the movement of

executive elements of the modules, development of work organization schemes and programming [19] of executive movements of technological modules with their involvement in the system of construction works.

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